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Combination of experimental and computational approaches: Recent development in catalytic organic and bioorganic reactions

In the last few decades, catalyzed organic and bioorganic reactions have attracted much attention in chemical and pharmaceutical researches. Recently, the design of novel catalysts and enzymes are in much demands to circumvent certain intractable synthetic problems